

ISic3636

I.Sicily inscription 3636

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mazara

Place of origin (modern)

Mazara del Vallo

Provenance

seen in 1827 on a sarcophagus in the Cathedral

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645705

EDCS 59500343

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2010.0612

Kragelund, P. 2008. Roman inscriptions from Ferrara, Mazara and Nîmes in the papers of Børge Thorlacius (1775-1829). *Classica et Mediaevalia*. 59: 117-122. At

120-121

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